

THE IMPORTANCE OF GIVING CLEAR INSTRUCTIONS IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: *The article is dedicated to the study of various researchers' viewpoints on the importance of giving clear instructions to students for the lessons to be effective and motivating.*

Key words: *loud and clear voice, attention, simple, imperative, easy to understand, specific, concise, frustration.*

First of all, When should we give instructions?

We give instructions at all times! If we want people to do something specific for us, or if someone asks how to do things, or how to assemble things we read instructions. So we should give instructions BEFORE a task, in our case, before a task-based activity so that it can go well and smoothly.

Why is it important to give clear instructions?

- Students will understand it the first time;
- It avoids misunderstandings;
- You don't need to repeat yourself;
- You don't need to repeat it individually;
- You won't waste time;
- Activities will flow;
- Students will do exactly what you asked.

Remember that it also applies to your lives. If you are giving instructions to other people instead of your students, you also have to do them clearly to avoid the problems mentioned above.

So how can we do it properly? There are a few simple steps:

1. Give clear and simple instructions.

Use simple words and phrases in the present simple, imperative, or be going to depending on your intention. Good examples of simple and clear instructions are: *"I want you to sit down and open your books to page 18"* or *"You are going to sit*

down and open your books to page 18". Another way is by being direct "*Sit down. Open your books to page 18*".

2. Break too long instructions.

Sometimes you have lots of instructions to give, so break them into parts. Instead of saying: "*You are going to sit down, open your books to page 18 and do activity 6. You are going to put the name of an activity you like and draw it on the side*", say this: "*I want you to sit down and open your books to page 18. (wait for students to do what is asked) Look at activity six. Write the name of the activity you like most and draw it on the side*". Can you see the difference?

3. Demonstrate.

Use the words "*for example*". If you feel that the instructions are too complicated, simply invite a volunteer and model the activity to the class.

4. Ask Instructions Checking Questions (ICQs).

It is not good to use "*Do you have any questions?*" at all times. Sometimes the students lie and don't tell you that they didn't get anything – not because they are bad students, but because they feel embarrassed to be in the spotlight. So try using ICQs, for example: "*Are you going to first draw or write your name?*"

5. Ask "*Do you have any questions?*"

But sometimes using this question is not wrong, specially if you tried ICQs first.

6. Hand out papers or say "*Turn to page...*"

One very important step, especially with kids is handing out things. Just hand your material to your students once you explained it, otherwise, they will forget that you exist and start doing the activity before you ask them to do so. Later they will have lots of questions related to the thing you have just explained but they were not paying attention.

7. Say, "*Please start*"

Last, but not least... be polite! Whenever you want them to do things, say "*please*". People will enjoy it and they tend to do it faster and happily.

Tips to give good instructions:

How can we give good instructions after all?

- Always get students' attention;
- Start with the main verbs – imperatives (it keeps sentences clear/short/simple);
- Speak loud and clear;
- Grade your language;
- Show-don't give;

- Use visuals/*Realia*;
- Check understanding: either/or questions;
- Give examples;
- Use keywords / Give logical aspects;
- Use gestures.

By following these steps I'm sure your classes will be much better.

To make your instructions CLEAR

What can we teachers do to make our instructions clear?

Here is a list of 10 simple steps you can follow:

1. Get students' attention. Gather the group together and signal you are about to tell students what to do. You can do so by putting up a hand and/or asking for silence. It is of paramount importance that you wait until you do get full silence. If you don't, you will most probably have to go over your explanation again once those students who were still chatting pay attention to you.

2. Be clear, specific and concise. (Breiburd, Nacamuli Klebs & Vázquez, 2017). Three conditions need to be met: instructions need to be specific which means "relating to one thing and not others" (Cambridge Dictionary), i.e. being precise and specified; concise, which involves "expressing or covering much in few words" (www.Thesaurus.com). Also, your instructions need to be easy to understand. Therefore, refer to one particular thing at a time, and avoid over-lengthy, 'over-wordy' explanations, which may confuse students with too much information that is not needed. At lower levels use simple language (no complex structures), short sentences, and true cognates (transparent words) where possible.

3. Project your voice. Classrooms may be quite big and may hold a large number of students. Therefore, you need to choose a spot in the room where your voice reaches everyone and all students can hear what you are about to say.

4. Provide visual support. Use gestures and body language wherever suitable and possible. Back in 1967, Dr. Albert Mehrabian broke human communication into three components: words, which account for 7%; tone of voice, 38%; and body language, 55%. This means that what we say carries only 7% of the message. And, although not all researchers agree with that number, everyone does agree that non-verbal communication overshadows verbal. If most of a message is conveyed by communication which exceeds words, our instructions will need to reflect that as well.

5. Assumptions. Do not take for granted that students understood what you have explained. Dartnell (n.d., p.1) claims that "the message received might differ from what we actually meant." She also reminds us of the saying 'assumption is

the mother of all mistakes'. Even if most of our students may be focused and 'tuned-in', this may not be the case for all. As a result, you will need to take a further step before you set the activity going, which is 'checking' they have understood what is required of them.

6. Checking. Seek for an explanation on the part of the students where they state two things: what the nature of the task is (i.e. what the task consists of) and a description of the behaviors that are expected from them. This may take, for e.g., the form of one student 'paraphrasing' what the teacher has said. Let them use the language they handle: remember that other students may find it easier to understand utterances at their own level of interlanguage rather than complex book rubrics. Personally I believe that at beginner levels, some L1 may also be allowed, since the purpose of this step is to clarify what to do, rather than to test how much English they can produce.

Another way of checking is doing a dry-run or a practice-run (i.e. a rehearsal), where students will see the activity in action and how to solve it.

7. Complex tasks. Break down a complex activity into simpler and shorter steps. This will keep the whole group advancing together more or less at the same speed, and will prevent students from losing the overall thread. A few key words numbered on the board to keep students focused is a good idea as well.

8. Mark the beginning of the activity. This will help you maintain the pace of the lesson, as, since all students will start at the same time, most students will end (more or less) at the same time.

9. Assign a time limit. Remember that it is the teacher's job to allot how much time each activity takes, which is of paramount relevance to maintain the momentum throughout the lesson (Richards & Lockhart 1994). Also, students need to be aware of how much the activity takes so that they organize their own time.

10. Warning! If you notice any problem crops up, there are misinterpretations or the meaning of a word/ couple of words is blocking the right development of the activity, do not try to solve it on a one-student-at-a-time basis. Just stop the activity as a whole, gather students' attention, repair misunderstandings, mark the new beginning, and let students finish the activity.

Last but not least, remember that after you have given proper, clear instructions and students start working, walking around and monitoring their work is always a good idea!

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